

Aerial Aqueducts: Towards a New Era in Firefighting

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Abstract

Wildfires are a growing global threat that require effective prevention and control strategies. A novel fire suppression system is proposed, using a fleet of specialized and interconnected “firecraft” that pump water from nearby sources—such as rivers, lakes, seas, or dedicated fire hydrants—and disperse it through a continuous downpour over and around wildfire areas to effectively suppress the blaze. Key advantages of such a system include its potential for rapid response capability, making it particularly effective for controlling large wildfires in remote and inaccessible areas. While developing such a system may present technical and logistical challenges, these obstacles can be addressed through careful planning and innovation, without undermining its overall feasibility. Beyond its ability to quickly suppress fires, the system offers the potential to protect critical environmental resources, wildlife habitats, and biodiversity, making it a viable option that warrants exploration and investment to mitigate the broader ecological impacts of wildfires.

Keywords: Aerial firefighting; disaster mitigation; fire suppression; Firecraft; aquacraft; firefighting; remote terrain firefighting; fire risk analysis; fire technology; wildfire management.

Wildfires are pervasive forces of destruction in many parts of the world, as demonstrated by the increasing frequency of mega-fires. In Canada, for example, the situation was particularly dire in 2023, with an alarming expanse of up to 18 million hectares succumbing to the blaze, as reported by The Canadian Interagency Forest Fire Centre (CIFFC)*.

Recent fires in Los Angeles, USA, caused major destruction, damaging homes, businesses, and natural landscapes†. This disaster highlights the urgent need to develop more efficient and rapid fire suppression systems to better protect communities and the environment from future fires.

While measures such as early warning systems, remote sensing, and enhanced land-use planning in high-risk areas are implemented, the efficacy of such methods are often limited particularly in remote and large forested areas. Substantial damage occurs before a fire can be successfully contained. Therefore, swift and effective fire suppression systems are required. Suppression fire by laser is already proposed [1]. Here, an approach centered around a fleet of "Fire Suppression Aircraft" (Aqua-Craft, Fire-crafts, or Artificial rain-crafts) is proposed, based on a continuous water supply from above until the fire is extinguished (Fig 1).

Here is how this conceptual system can work:

- 1) **Fire detection and system activation:** Upon detecting a wildfire and informing fire authorities, an immediate response is activated, dispatching a fleet of Fire Suppression Aircraft to the scene. Prior to takeoff, the system should identify the nearest open water source, which could be a lake, river, or sea, using specialized GPS or radar systems, enabling precise navigation of the firefighting aircraft to the location. If none of these options are available, it will be essential to implement specialized fire hydrants adapted to work with this framework in regions at high fire risks.
- 2) **Connecting to water source:** A first aircraft flies over a water source close to the wildfire, extending its water pipe into the source. Then, the aircraft ascends vertically to an optimal altitude, which could range from 500 to 1000 meters, or be adjustable to less or more than

* <https://www.ciffc.ca>

† <https://www.fire.ca.gov>

this range as necessary based on the fire's scale and intensity. In areas where natural open water sources are unavailable, dedicated fire hydrants, adapted for use with a fire-craft system to extinguish fires from above, can be implemented and placed within forests and high-fire risk regions to be used at need.

- 3) **Extending the pipe:** A second aircraft in the sequence maneuvers itself ahead and establishes a connection by extending its water pipe to interlink with the water reservoir of the preceding aircraft (Fig 1). This procedure can be likened to in-flight refueling process to fuel flying aircraft through interconnected pipelines. The spacing between the aircraft may vary, depending on the size of the fire, water pressure, and pipe diameter, durability and flexibility. For example, aquacraft vertical spacing can be adjusted to more or less than the vertical distance above the water source (500 to 1000 meters), or any distance determined empirically to best suit the prevailing conditions. Factors such as diameter, solidity, and elasticity of pipelines play a role in determining the horizontal distance between aircraft. The purpose of arranging aircraft in a chain “or train” is essential to ensure uninterrupted support for pipes, preventing potential cracking due to water pressure. However, when the distance between fire sites and an open water source is short and manageable, deploying a few or only one aquacraft connected to the water source becomes a viable alternative to a chain of aircraft, without the need for continuous adjacent support.
- 4) **Aquacraft chain formation:** As the operation unfolds, additional aircraft can gradually join the aerial chain. Each of these aircraft extends its water pipe to the preceding one by an adequate distance as needed. The gradual expansion of aquacraft creates an interconnected network above and/or around the wildfire site. Fire-crafts could adjust their positions, altitude, and vertical and horizontal spacing. The distances between the aircrafts and length of the pipes may vary, depending on water pumping logistics and pipe resistance. The closer the water source, the fewer crafts are needed, and vice versa.
- 5) **Uninterrupted water supply:** The water supply procedure begins with the first aircraft to fill its tanks and subsequent aircraft draw water from the tank of the preceding one and so on. Another possibility is that the firefighting aircraft could serve as supports for water pipelines between the leading and trailing craft. In this scenario, the aircraft would not carry water reservoirs but would instead hold the pipelines during the extinguishing process. The required water volumes for firefighting could be determined by wildfire's

intensity and the burning surface. The greater the intensity and spread of the fire, the higher the required volume of water. In all cases, continuous water pumping is maintained as long as the fire persists. Therefore, this approach is particularly suitable for coastal forests and those located near water sources.

- 6) **Synchronized fire suppression:** Once the tanks are filled with water, the aircraft closest to the fire site initiates a coordinated spraying operation, simulating an artificial rain effect. The aquacrafts should be designed to maneuver above and around the fire, moving back and forth, up and down, and side to side, as needed, until the flames are completely extinguished. Fire-craft should have the flexibility and capability to maneuver and navigate in all directions in order to effectively and efficiently manage and extinguish fires.
- 7) **Shutdown and retrieval:** When the fire is successfully extinguished, the first aircraft halts water pumping and the last one stops its “raining” while retracting its water pipe and equipment, followed by the remaining aircraft. Each aircraft retracts its pipe and returns to its station.
- 8) **Automated oversight:** The system's operation can be monitored and controlled through central automated mechanisms. An algorithm calculates the optimal number of aircraft, their spacing, and the altitude above the fire site, based on pipe length and distance to the water source and fire size. An automated approach allows a rapid activation and results in efficiency and timely extinguishing of fires. A balance between fleet's safety and efficiency of firefighting should always be maintained.

Advantages

The proposed model of suppressing wildfires through artificial rain crafts could have a wide range of environmental and societal benefits, including:

- **Swift and effective fire suppression:** Ensuring a continuous water supply allows large and remote wildfires, which typically pose major challenges, to be extinguished within a short timeframe—ranging from minutes to a few hours—depending on the fire size, site configuration, and the distance of the water source.
- **Minimized impact and toxicity:** Quickly containing flames greatly reduces overall damage to natural landscapes and human environments. This proactive approach plays a critical role

in preserving biodiversity, property, and human lives. The system is particularly relevant in mountainous and coastal regions where wildfires are frequent.

- Since it relies solely on water, there is no environmental toxicity associated with chemicals, foam, or gases. Additionally, reduced human exposure to fire minimizes the risks faced by firefighting personnel. A water-based, rapid fire suppression system protects plant and animal communities, infrastructure, and natural resources.
- Homes, agricultural lands, and essential services are shielded from the destructive force of wildfires, fostering economic and societal stability. A notable advantage of this system is its ability to combat fires in high-rise buildings, mountainous areas, and steep slopes that are difficult to access with conventional methods. The aerial nature of the solution allows for effective intervention in rugged terrains, tall structures, and remote locations.

Minimizing dependence on chemical-based fire retardants, such as ammonium polyphosphate (found in Phos-Chek), phosphate-based retardants, sodium-based retardants, and aqueous film-forming foam, which are often deployed in traditional methods to combat wildfires, reduces the toxicity associated with these chemicals. The use of firefighting aircraft that rely solely on water for extinguishing wildfires, as suggested here, offers an environmentally safer solution.

- **Applications in prevention and irrigation:** Functioning as specialized "rain-crafts," aerial aqueducts can offer innovative solutions for both fire prevention and irrigation. During periods of elevated fire risk, these aircraft can be used proactively to disperse water over vulnerable areas, mitigating the threat of fires while providing moisture to plants and animals in need. Aircraft of this kind can serve as precise irrigation tools, delivering essential moisture where and when it is required, especially in areas where freshwater sources are distant. In regions with abundant freshwater resources, such as lakes and rivers, the proposed "rain-crafts" can operate as targeted artificial rain systems, effectively addressing local drought conditions in areas facing water scarcity.

Considerations & Precautions

The concept of employing a fleet of fire-crafts or rain-crafts equipped with a continuous water supply system for extinguishing wildfires is a promising approach. However, the feasibility of this method depends on a variety of factors that include:

- **Infrastructure and technology requirements:** Fighting fires is fundamentally an engineering challenge on a planetary scale. Achieving a continuous water-supply fire-craft system requires advancements in aircraft engineering, automation, and water pumping technologies, as well as effective methods for conveying water through airborne pipelines over extended distances and altitudes. The viability of such a system will depend on access to advanced technology and the capability to manufacture and maintain fire-crafts and their associated equipment.

However, the technology landscape has progressed substantially in both infrastructure and aircraft engineering. The oil industry for instance effectively manages complex processes, such as extracting oil from important depths and transporting it through extensive pipelines spanning thousands of kilometers. Groundwater is also pumped from thousands of meters below the surface in some regions. Adapting similar technologies to pump water from open water sources or dedicated hydrant through specialized fire-craft could help turn this concept into a practical solution for mitigating wildfires worldwide.

- **Allocation of funding and resources:** Developing such technology would require substantial investments. However, when comparing the cost of fires to the development of this proposal, it is worth the investment. The annual cost of fires in the U.S. alone is staggering, reaching up to \$893 billion every year according to U.S. Senate reports. If a portion of the global costs of fire damage were redirected toward developing this solution, the potential benefits could be considerable and quickly recovered. Commitment of resources from governments, private entities, or international collaborations could play a crucial role in transforming this approach into a tangible reality. Furthermore, the proposed system could be manufactured and sold to other countries as a business opportunity.

When freshwater is scarce or seawater is used as the extinguishing agent, it's crucial to assess the sustainability of the freshwater source and the potential ecological effects of seawater. However, employing seawater to extinguish fires would likely not be worse than the existing mixtures currently used in fire suppression. Using seawater as an extinguishing agent might cause a slight increase in salinity at the fire site, but this increase would pale in comparison to the extensive ramifications of uncontrolled wildfires. Since wildfires predominantly occur in forested, remote, or coastal areas, any salinity caused by saltwater

would remain localized. The salts deposited at the fire site could even serve as fertilizers for subsequent plant growth.

- **Adherence to regulations and permission:** Operating fire-craft within airspace must adhere to aviation regulations, safety protocols, and air traffic management to minimize the risk of accidents. Developing autonomous fire-craft can further reduce the potential for incidents involving pilots. Before widespread deployment, rigorous testing and validation of the fire-craft system under real conditions are essential to ensure its functionality, reliability, and safety.

Conclusion

Climate change is expected to increase the intensity and frequency of wildfires worldwide, causing substantial environmental and economic losses. Developing efficient firefighting solutions is essential to reduce damage and protect natural resources and biodiversity. One promising approach is to develop an aircraft system that simulates natural rainfall, using an aerial fleet interconnected with nearby water sources, such as lakes, rivers, or dedicated fire hydrants, to ensure a continuous water supply. Such a system could represent an important advancement over traditional fire suppression methods, which typically involve dropping fixed quantities of water or fire retardant in intervals, making them slower and less efficient compared to a controlled, continuous water supply delivered by an interconnected fleet of aircraft. While developing such a system may seem costly, complex and challenging, its overall cost is likely to be lower than the annual economic and human costs of wildfires, including loss of life, damage to infrastructure, and destruction of biodiversity. The value of even a single human life lost to fire far exceeds the financial investment required to create this solution. Historically, more complex projects—such as space and planetary exploration—were often considered costly, dangerous, or unrealistic. Spacecraft and airplanes, once mere concepts, are now a reality. Similarly, the development of firecraft equipped with a continuous water supply is not only feasible and cost-effective when compared to space exploration programs, but it is also highly practical, useful, and urgently needed, especially given the escalating climate challenges and the increasing risks of wildfires. Investments in such a system would quickly offset the substantial annual losses in human lives, crop yields, forests, and infrastructure caused by frequent and intensive wildfires.

References

1. Moustafa, K., *Laser to fight fire?* J Emerg Manag, 2020. **18**(5): p. 455-456.

**Aquacraft fleet
or automated fire drones
connected to each other**

Dedicated fire hydrants can be used as an alternative water supply when natural open water sources are unavailable

Fig. 1 A proposal to extinguish wildfires using a continuous water supply provided by specialized fire craft equipped with dedicated water tanks, reels, and stretchable water pipes. When a fire is detected, a fleet of fire craft promptly responds, quelling the flames swiftly, mimicking natural rain, thanks to an uninterrupted water supply from nearby water bodies (lakes, rivers, or the sea/ocean). The process begins with the first craft dipping its water pipe into the source before ascending to an optimal altitude (approximately 500-1000 meters), depending on the surrounding landscape, site topography, distance to the fire, fire size and intensity, etc. Subsequent crafts take positions, each extending its water pipe to connect with the one before, forming a linked network that advances towards the fire site in a coordinated and controlled manner. Once all the aircraft are well-positioned, the first craft begins pumping water to fill its tanks. The second craft draws water from the first's tank, initiating a synchronized sequence that continues until all tanks are replenished. At full capacity, the fire-craft closest to the fire engage in a coordinated spraying operation, dousing the flames with a continuous stream of water. The crafts can maneuver in all directions for precise fire control and extinguishment. Alternatively, instead of onboard tanks or reservoirs, subsequent fire-craft can act as carriers or supports for the water pipe, extending it from the first craft to the required length to reach the fire site. Upon extinguishing the fire, the process reverses. The last crafts signal the others to cease pumping water, and the last craft in the chain initiates the retrieval of its water pipe, followed by the preceding one, and so on. Each fire craft retracts its own pipe and returns to its designated station. By using the power of a continuous water supply, this interconnected Fire-Craft approach can introduce a new era in firefighting, capable of effectively combating wildfires, safeguarding lives, and preserving natural landscapes. In regions without natural open water sources, dedicated fire hydrants (as shown in the figure), adapted for use with a fire-craft system to extinguish fires from above, can be placed within forests or high-fire-risk areas for use as needed.